

Effect of Machining Parameters on the Surface Roughness of Medium Carbon Steel Using Lathe Machine

Ayanam Bassey Sam, Aondona Paul Ihom ,
Idorenyin E. Markson, Emmanuel Udama Odeh

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Sam, A.B., Ihom, A.P., Markson, I.E., & Odeh, E.U. (2024). Effect of Machining Parameters on the Surface Roughness of Medium Carbon Steel Using Lathe Machine. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 798-817.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).68](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).68)

Abstract:

The service life of a machined part depends greatly on the quality of its surface roughness value. Depending on the requirements of the intended service life, machined parts may be smooth or rough. Therefore, the quality of surface finish of machined parts must be closely monitored by technicians, artisans and operators in the shop floor in order to achieve optimal output from machining operations. The quality of surface finish obtained through machining operations are affected by a number of factors. However, the most important factors are the cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut. These are the parameters that directly affect the characteristics of the surface

roughness value of a machined component. In this study, an investigation was carried out on the effect of machining parameters on the surface roughness of 0.3% medium carbon steel using the Lathe. All other factors inherent in the cutting operations was held as constant whilst the cutting parameters were intermittently varied. For each combination of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut, the corresponding value for surface roughness was measured and recorded. The methods of analyses chosen for this study were artificial neural network, response surface methodology and the factorial design. Findings from the study show that the result from artificial neural network and the factorial design method exhibited similar patterns with the results of previous studies which recorded that feed rate was the most significant parameter affecting surface roughness. Also, findings revealed that increasing feed rate, cutting speed and depth of cut would result in a corresponding increase in the surface roughness values. Results obtained through response surface methodology generally did not agree with most of the findings of previous works in literature. Based on the predictive capabilities of the three models, statistical metrics indicated that the ANN model was found to be the best model with a coefficient of determination of 0.9979 and a mean square error of 0.003017. This was followed by the factorial design model with a coefficient of determination of 0.9298 and a mean square error of 0.0980. The model from the response surface methodology came last with a coefficient of determination of 0.9600 and a MSE of 0.1008. From the findings, it is strongly recommended that values of feed rate must be systematically selected during machining operations and the models developed could be used to predict the surface roughness of 0.3% medium carbon steel by technicians and artisans on the shop floor.

Keywords: *Steel, Surface roughness, Machining parameters, Artificial neural networks, Response surface methodology, Factorial design.*

Introduction

Steel is an indispensable element in our everyday lives, playing a crucial role in numerous applications across various industries. For instance, in the automotive sector, steel is extensively utilized in the manufacturing of axles, gears, and crankshafts, which serve as vital components. Its versatility is further evident in the building and construction industry, where steel is predominantly employed in the fabrication of rods and support structures. The aviation field also heavily relies on steel as a primary material for the production of critical aircraft components.

Moreover, steel finds practical utility in domestic environments, manifesting in the creation of burglar-proofing systems, kitchen equipment, security architecture for smart homes, as well as household furniture and fittings. The breadth of steel's applications extends far beyond the aforementioned examples, demonstrating its seemingly limitless versatility. Notably, the various types of steel comprise carbon steels, stainless steels, alloy steels, and tool steels, as outlined by Sam, (2024).

Carbon steels belong to a class of steels where iron serves as the predominant constituent, accompanied by substantial proportions of carbon by weight and minute traces of other elements as impurities. Carbon steels are commonly designated as: low carbon steel, medium carbon steel, and high carbon steel. Medium carbon steel, in particular, finds extensive applications in the production of forgings, crankshafts, axles, tubes, plates, and constructional steels (Sheila, 2009; Alabi, *et al.*, 2010).

For manufacturing industries that rely on carbon steel as a primary raw material, it is imperative to maintain optimal quality of the parts used in production while minimizing recurring expenses. To fulfil these requirements, machinists and technicians operating on the shop floor must ensure that the surface integrity of the utilized parts meets the predefined minimum standards established by the relevant governing bodies.

The surface integrity of a machined component encompasses a comprehensive set of information pertaining to the quality of its solid surface. An essential aspect of surface integrity is surface roughness, which quantifies the presence of both macro and micro irregularities on the finished surface subsequent to the machining process (Sam, 2024). Fundamental industrial prerequisites for machined parts, including visual appearance, resistance to corrosion, wear, and fatigue, lubrication, dimensional tolerances, and pressure-holding capability, are closely intertwined with the quality of surface roughness (Sam., 2024). Sam, (2024) conducted a study on roughness parameters, illustrating that multiple factors describe specific defined characteristics of surface roughness. The authors emphasized that the amplitude parameters are crucial for characterizing surface topography. Essentially, these parameters are utilized to quantify the vertical aspects of surface irregularities.

In machining operations, a diverse array of machine tools including lathes, drilling machines, as well as horizontal and vertical milling machines, are utilized. Among these machining techniques, turning operations stands as the foremost operation employed for metal shaping due to the extensive range of operating conditions it offers in the modern industry (Pankaj *et al.*, 2017).

Turning may be described as a metal or material removal process in which rotational components are fashioned by eliminating surplus material. The machining process involves the use of a lathe or turning machine, a work piece, a fixture, and a cutting tool. The work piece is the material (or metal) that requires turning or shaping into a desired size or diameter. It is securely attached to the fixture which is then fastened to the turning machine (lathe) and allowed to rotate at high speeds. The cutter is usually a single-point cutting tool that is also fixed in the machine. It moves into the rotating work piece and removes material in the form of small chips to create the desired shape. In turning, the speed and movement of the cutting tool are determined by various parameters. These parameters are chosen for each operation based on factors such

as the material of the work piece, tool material, tool size, and other considerations.

The ultimate result in turning operations is to obtain machined surfaces with high dimensional accuracy, good surface finish and high reliability in its service life. Many factors have been found to affect the quality of turned surfaces but the evidently dominating factors as reported by Prasad (2013), are factors due to machining parameters (speed, feed rate, depth of cut) and the tool geometry (back rake, side rake). Several researchers and studies have unanimously agreed that the basic parameters affecting the turning operation of plain carbon steel are the cutting speed, the feed rate and the depth of cut. These parameters may be varied to obtain optimum values for different grades of steel. However, other factors affecting the machining condition are work-piece material, cutting fluid, the tool material and shape and surface finish amongst others.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effects of machining parameters on the

surface roughness of medium carbon steel on the lathe. The lathe is a very common machine tool in every mechanical and production engineering workshop. From the result generated predictive models will be developed using ANN, factorial design, and response surface methodology models which shall be validated using statistical metrics and previous data.

Materials and Method

Materials

Steel samples were acquired and sent for chemical analysis at the Defence Industry Corporation of Nigeria, Kaduna (DICON). Results obtained from this analysis indicated that the selected work-piece contain 0.3% carbon indicating a medium carbon category. Table 1 shows the chemical composition in percentage (by weight) of the various elements present in the work-piece chosen for the experiment.

Table 1. Chemical Composition of Work-piece

Element Percentage Composition							
C %	Si %	Mn %	P %	S %	Cr %	Ni %	Mo %
0.323	0.059	0.57	0.0066	0.024	0.011	0.037	<0.0020
Al %	Cu %	Co %	Ti %	Nb %	V %	W %	Pb %
0.0032	0.038	0.0056	<0.0010	<0.0040	<0.0010	0.020	<0.0030
Mg %	B %	Sn %	Zn %	As %	Bi %	Ca %	Ce %
<0.0010	0.0006	0.0051	0.0026	0.0027	0.0054	0.0009	<0.0030
Zr %	La %	Fe					
<0.0015	<0.0010	98.9					

Source: Field data from DICON, 2019

Equipment

The data in Table 1 indicating the chemical composition of the work-piece material was obtained with the aid of the Spectromaxx metal analyser (MAXx LMF14) at DICON in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spectromaxx Metal Analyser (MAXx LMF14)

Source: DICON, 2019

The engine Lathe (EMCO Maximat Super II) was used for this experiment.

Method

The work-piece material of 12.5 mm in diameter and 711.2 mm in length was cut into 7 pieces of approximately 101.6 mm in length each. Straight turning operation was employed for the experiment. The cutting tool employed for this operation was high speed steel. The cutting fluid used throughout the turning experiments was soluble oil. Soluble oil was considered for the turning operation because it contains mineral oil, emulsifiers, rust inhibitors and bactericide (Sulaiman *et al.*, 2020). The available range of speeds provided by the Lathe were 55-2200 rpm and the available range of feed provided were 0.03 - 0.3 mm/rev. From these ranges, selected values of the cutting speed (55 rpm, 200 rpm and 300 rpm), feed rate (0.15 mm/rev, 0.21 mm/rev) were considered suitable for the experiments. This selection was based on the fact that the above combination of cutting speeds and feed rates were frequently used in turning operations performed on the machine in the workshop. Consequently, the selected values of the cutting

or machining parameters (variables) for the turning operation were set up as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Selected Values of Cutting Parameters on Lathe (EMCO Maximat Super II)

Cutting Speed (rpm)	Feed Rate (mm/rev)	Depth of Cut (mm)
55	0.15	0.25
55	0.21	0.35
200	0.15	0.75
200	0.21	0.35
300	0.15	0.25
300	0.21	0.75

Source: Field data, 2021

The values of D_0 and D_1 were measured with the aid of Vernier calliper and mathematically determined using equation:

$$(D_0 - D_1)/2 \quad (1)$$

Where

D_0 = diameter of work-piece before machining and

D_1 = diameter of work-piece after machining

At the end of the experiments, the machined work-pieces were labelled A to F (for each combination of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut) for clarity and taken for surface roughness measurements. The Elcometer 224 device depicted in Figure 2 was employed to measure surface roughness. Specifically, for this research, the R_a parameter was utilized to quantify surface roughness. Table 3 presents the data illustrating the specific combinations of cutting parameters along with their corresponding values of measured surface roughness.

Figure 2. The Elcometer 224

Method of Data Analysis

Three (3) methods of data analyses were employed for this study. The analytical tools chosen were artificial neural network, response surface methodology and full factorial design. The data in Table 3 was further expanded using the “Rand function” in Microsoft Excel. Five hundred (500) data points were generated from the original data using this function (Sam, 2024). These data points were used to perform the analyses in artificial neural network, response surface methodology and full factorial design.

Table 3. Selected Cutting Parameters with Respective Values of Surface Roughness

Cutting Speed (rpm)	Feed Rate (mm/rev)	Depth of Cut (mm)	Surface Roughness Value (μm)
55	0.15	0.25	1.62
55	0.21	0.35	2.20
200	0.15	0.75	0.52
200	0.21	0.35	3.79
300	0.15	0.25	1.43
300	0.21	0.75	0.95

Source: Field data, 2021

Artificial Neural Network

In this study, the neural network toolbox within MATLAB 2015a mathematical software was utilized for the prediction of steel surface roughness. The configuration selected for the ANN model is detailed in Table 2.1. In the MATLAB software, one hundred and twenty-

five data points (See Sam, 2024) were extracted from the generated 500 data points and partitioned into three distinct sets: the training set (70%), test set (15%) and validation set (15%). During the training phase, the neural network adjusts the neuron weights using the training data, ensuring optimal adaptation. Concurrently, validation data assesses the network's generalization capability. Subsequently, the finalized network undergoes evaluation using testing data to verify its performance. The criteria for halting the training process are typically defined by predetermined error metrics (e.g., mean square error, MSE) or when the specified number of training epochs, typically set to 1000 by default, is reached. However, in this investigation, the number of training epochs was specifically designated as 1000.

Table 4. Parameter Settings for ANN model

Parameters	Values
Training data set	87 (70% of dataset)
Testing data set	19 (15% of dataset)
Validation data set	19 (15% of dataset)
Number of hidden layers	1
Number of neurons in hidden layer	1 – 20
Activation function (hidden layer)	Tansig
Activation function (output layer)	Purelin
Number of epochs	1000
Learning rate	0.70
Architecture selection	Trial and error
Target goal mean square error	10^{-5}
Minimum performance gradient	10^{-5}

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

Response Surface Methodology

In response surface analysis, the design type selected for this study was the central composite rotatable design (CCRD). The analysis and formulation of model equations for surface roughness were conducted using the Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) software package

within the Minitab environment, specializing in design of experiments. Four different models namely; linear, two factorial interactions (2FI), quadratic, and cubic were used to analyse the responses and the models were fitted to the experimental data using Design Expert Software. The selected model for design was the quadratic model. Based on this design, twenty (20) data points as indicated in Sam, (2024) were extracted from the five hundred (500) generated data points were used to perform the analysis. The coded and actual factors, their levels and the response values as extracted are also given in Sam. (2024).

Factorial design

In the factorial design analysis, the design type selected for this study was the full factorial design. The Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package was utilized for the design of experiments and analysis to generate model equations for surface roughness, following the principles of the response surface method. The selected model for this design was the two factorial interaction (2FI). Based on this design, the same one hundred and twenty-five (125) data points in Sam, (2024), that were used

to perform the analysis in ANN were also utilized for the factorial design analysis. The coded and actual factors, their levels and the interval of variation for the factorial design as extracted are given in Sam, (2024).

Results and Discussion

Results on Artificial Neural Network

Performance of the ANN model

This section examines the effectiveness of various network architectures with regards to training, testing, and validation. Considering that the main goal of a trained Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is to enhance prediction accuracy, it is posited that the performance of a specific ANN when evaluated with test data should serve as the benchmark for determining the optimal ANN architecture.

Through extensive trials, it was discovered that an artificial neural network (ANN) with three neurons in the hidden layer yielded the most favourable performance, achieving a validation MSE of 0.0019568. The optimal structure of the ANN model is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Optimal Architecture of the Neural Network

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

In this ANN configuration, training halted at 71 epochs for a 3-3-1 architecture, thus, achieving a validation mean squared error (MSE) of 0.0019568, as illustrated in Figure 4. Consequently, the 3-3-1 configuration is deemed one of the superior neural networks for the current problem at hand, owing to its robust

predictive accuracy marked by an MSE of 0.0019568. The network's remarkable predictive power is attributed to the optimal count of hidden layer neurons chosen to accurately fit the model. This is to prevent an under-fitting of the model or over-fitting of the model.

Figure 4. Neural Network Validation Performance

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

The predicted model (or equation) demonstrates an exceptional fit to the true values within the training, testing, and validation datasets. This is evidenced by the correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.99706, 0.9979, and 0.9985 for the training, testing, and validation datasets, respectively, as presented in Table 5.

The scatter plots depicted in Figure 5 illustrate the proposed models' predicted surface roughness values against the actual experimental results for the training, validation, and testing datasets. The model's predictions align closely with the experimental values, as evidenced by the high correlation coefficients (R) for the training, testing, and validation sets. The rationale behind this assertion is that the closer the correlation coefficient is to 1, the more accurate the model's performance. However, relying solely on correlation coefficients as the basis for determining an artificial neural network (ANN) model's predictive capability is not always advised. The reason lies in the fact that a model may exhibit a strong correlation coefficient yet still perform poorly in prediction when subjected to new data sets that were not utilized during the ANN training process.

Development of the ANN Model

The model developed by applying The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm, (ρ_f) is presented in Equation 3.1.

$$\rho_f = \sum_{j=1}^3 \{ \text{purelin}[LW_{j,1}(\sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \text{tansig}(X_i * IW_{i,j} + b_1))] + b_2 \} \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 denotes a trained ANN model that correlates the three input parameters and the final downhole mud density in MATLAB. In this context, 'purelin' and 'tansig' are MATLAB activation functions that calculate the layer's output from its network input. The purelin function establishes a linear relationship between the input and the output, with the underlying algorithm being $\text{purelin}(n) = n$. Conversely, the tansig function is a hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer function, which is mathematically equivalent to the tanh operation. While tansig is computationally faster than tanh in MATLAB simulations, it is commonly utilized in neural network architectures. The tansig relation is defined by the expression given in Equation 3.

$$\text{Tansig} = \frac{2}{(1 + \exp(-2 \text{network})) - 1} \quad (3)$$

LW and IW denote the weights of the connections from the output layer to the hidden layer and from the hidden layer to the input layer, respectively. To predict the surface roughness using Equation 2, the values presented in Table 6 are applied. Nonetheless, the x_i values in Equation 2 correspond to the individual data points for each input variable. Here, x represents the input variables, specifically cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut; N signifies the number of neurons (which is 3 in this situation); j indicates the number of input variables, which in this instance are three; b_1 is the bias of the hidden layer, and b_2 is the bias of the output layer. Table 6 details the weights and biases of the established empirical correlation (Equation 2) that can be utilized to predict the surface roughness of steel.

Table 5. Performance of ANN Model Using Three Error Metrics

	Samples	R ²	MSE	RMSE
Training	87	0.99706	0.00204895	0.0452
Validation	19	0.99859	0.00195679	0.0442
Testing	19	0.9979	0.00301706	0.0549

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

Figure 5. Scatter Plots of ANN model predictions

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

Table 6. Weights and Biases for ANN Model in Equation 2

IW			b ₁	LW	b ₂
-0.20651	0.272344	-3.1585	-0.85867	-0.04135	0.551812
-0.08075	0.142977	-0.04533	-0.00354	-7.03752	
0.1434	-0.52162	0.005809	0.21708	-3.13531	

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

For instance, when predicting surface roughness using cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut, the value of W_1 is assigned as $j=1$ for cuttings speed, at $j=2$ for feed rate and $j=3$ for depth of cut. Specifically, the term $\sum_{j=1}^j w_{1,j}x_j$ for steel surface roughness in Table 2.3 can be computed as follows; $\sum_{j=1}^j w_{1,j}x_j = w_{1,1}x_1 + w_{1,2}x_2 + w_{1,3}x_3$; where the values of $W_{1,1}$, $W_{1,2}$ and $W_{1,3}$ are -0.20651, 0.272344, -3.1585 respectively. This process is replicated for each of the three rows in the matrix, and the values that correlates for each row can be obtained from the Tables.

Explicit Representation of the Developed ANN Model

The established ANN model for estimating or predicting surface roughness (MSR) is presented in Equation 2. This model has been clarified by incorporating the weights and biases of the ANN model detailed in Table 6

.

$$SR = A + B + C + 0.551812$$

Where:

$$A = -0.04135 [\tanh(-0.20651CS + 0.272344FR - 3.1585DC - 0.85867)]$$

$$B = -7.03752 [\tanh(-0.08075CS + 0.142977FR - 0.04533DC - 0.00354)]$$

$$C = -3.13531 [\tanh(0.1434CS - 0.52162FR + 0.005809DC + 0.21708)]$$

And CS = cutting speed; FR = feed rate and DC = depth of cut and tanh = hyperbolic tangent

Discussion of Results from ANN

The objective of sensitivity analysis in ANN is to modify the input variables of the model and evaluate the resulting changes in model output. This approach is particularly valuable for identifying the model's weaknesses (Sam, 2024). Sensitivity analysis has thus provided means to

elucidate the extent of each input variable's contribution to the network. The impact of each input variable on predicting the dependent variable is termed the relative importance of that variable. Numerous methods for determining the relative importance of input variables are extensively discussed in the literature. Examples of such methods include Garson's algorithm, the connection weights algorithm, the use of partial derivatives, and Lek's profile method, among others. For this study, the connection weights algorithm was selected. This choice is based on the findings of Sam (2024), who compared various techniques for evaluating input variable contributions in ANNs and demonstrated that the connection weights method exhibited the least bias. This conclusion was further supported by Sam (2024).

The connection weights algorithm introduced by Sam, (2024) computes the sum of the products of the final weights linking input neurons to hidden neurons with those connecting hidden neurons to the output neuron, for all input neurons. The connection weights from input neurons to hidden neurons are indicated in columns 2 to 4 of Table 7, whereas the connection weights from hidden neurons to the output neuron are shown in column 5 of Table 4.3. The relative importance of a specific input variable is defined as illustrated in Equation 4.

$$RI_x = \sum_{y=1}^m w_{xy}w_{yz} \quad (4)$$

Here, RI_x represents the relative importance of input variable x . $\sum_{y=1}^m w_{xy}w_{yz}$ denotes the sum of product of final weights of the connection from the input neuron to the hidden neurons with the connection from hidden neurons to output neuron. In this context, y is the total number of hidden neurons, and z is the output neuron.

Table 7. Final Connection Weights

	Cutting speed (rpm)	Feed rate (mm/rev)	Depth of cut (mm)	Surface roughness (μm)
Hidden layer	Input 1	Input 2	Input 3	Output
1	-0.20651	0.272344	-3.1585	-0.04135
2	-0.08075	0.142977	-0.04533	-7.03752
3	0.1434	-0.52162	0.005809	-3.13531

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

The sum of the products of the connection weights and rank of the input variables is presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Connection Weights Products, Relative Importance and Rank of Inputs

Hidden nodes	Input No.1	Input No.2	Input No.3
1	0.066774104	-0.088061239	1.021287135
2	-4.778954844	8.461679588	-2.682724744
3	-0.385058443	1.400656801	-0.015598358
[Sum] S _j	-5.097239184	9.77427515	-1.677035966

	INPUT 1	INPUT 2	INPUT 3
RELATIVE IMPORTANCE (%)	30.84	59.13	10.15

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

Figure 6 illustrates the relative importance of the various input parameters. It should be noted that high sensitivity to a parameter indicates that the system’s performance can significantly change with minor variations in that parameter, and vice versa. Based on this analogy, it is evident that the process input variable, specifically the feed rate, has the most substantial impact on the surface roughness of steel, followed by cutting speed, and then the depth of cut. These findings align with and reflect what is reported in the literature. For example, Sam (2024) examined the effects of cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut on the dimensional accuracy and surface finish during dry turning of AISI 4340 (30 HRC) steel. They found that the feed rate had a significantly greater impact on surface roughness compared to cutting speed and depth of cut. Additionally, Senthil *et al.* (2013) investigated the influence of the three primary turning parameters on the machinability of homogenized Al–Cu/TiB₂ MMC. They observed a notable decrease in surface roughness when the cutting speed

increased from 50 to 100 m/min. Beyond this range, the roughness remained relatively stable. Surface roughness values increased sharply with rising feed rates, whereas the depth of cut had only a minor effect on surface roughness.

Figure 6. Relative Importance of Input Variables on Surface Roughness

Source: Extracted from MATLAB software, 2021

Results on Response Surface Methodology

Based on the model exhibiting the highest coefficient of determination (R^2) and the lowest standard deviation, the quadratic model was chosen for predicting the surface roughness of the turning operation. The analysis of variance

(ANOVA) for the selected quadratic model, with surface roughness serving as the response variable, is detailed in Table 9. Additionally, Table 10 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the variance analysis for the surface roughness response.

Table 9. ANOVA of Response Surface Quadratic Model for Surface Roughness (microns)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	10.76	9	1.20	31.34	< 0.0001	significant
A-Cutting Speed	0.8696	1	0.8696	22.79	0.0008	
B-Feed Rate	0.1914	1	0.1914	5.02	0.0490	
C-Depth of Cut	0.5006	1	0.5006	13.12	0.0047	
AB	0.0015	1	0.0015	0.0396	0.8462	
AC	0.3240	1	0.3240	8.49	0.0154	
BC	0.0946	1	0.0946	2.48	0.1464	
A ²	5.86	1	5.86	153.72	< 0.0001	
B ²	0.0051	1	0.0051	0.1330	0.7230	
C ²	4.08	1	4.08	107.01	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.3815	10	0.0381			
Lack of Fit	0.3797	5	0.0759	216.99	< 0.0001	Significant
Pure Error	0.0018	5	0.0004			
Cor Total	11.14	19				

Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Table 10. Analysis of Variance for the Response

Source	Df	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F- Value	P- Value
Model	9	10.76	1.20	31.34	0.0001
Cutting Speed	1	0.8696	0.8696	22.79	0.0008
Feed Rate	1	0.1914	0.1914	5.02	0.0490
Depth of Cut	1	0.5006	0.5006	13.12	0.0047
Error	10	0.3815	0.0381		
Lack-of-Fit	5	0.3797	0.0759	216.99	0.0001
Pure Error	5	0.0018	0.0004		
Total	19	11.14			

Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Discussion of Results from Response Surface Methodology

The final regression model for the surface roughness using RSM is given in Equation 5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Surface Roughness} = & +95.66727 X_3 \\
 & -0.018333 X_1 * X_2 \\
 & -0.080500 X_1 * X_3 \\
 & +145.00000 X_2 * X_3 \\
 & -15.43264 X_1^2 \\
 & +0.086699 X_1 -63.13131 X_2^2 \\
 & -32.47273 X_2 -161.18182 X_3^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Where X_1 denotes cutting speed, X_2 denotes feed rate and X_3 signifies the depth of cut. In the equation above, the positive terms signify a direct relationship between the independent variables (cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut) and the dependent variable (surface roughness). However, the negative terms indicate a reverse correlation (inverse relationship) between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Thus, it was noticed that the cutting speed and the depth of cut had a direct relationship with the surface roughness, while the feed rate had an indirect relationship on the surface roughness. This implies that increasing cutting speed and depth of cut values, gives rise to a corresponding increase in the value of the surface roughness while increasing

feed rate results in decreasing values of surface roughness. Moreover, based on the outcomes derived from the analysis of variance (ANOVA), it was determined that the cutting speed exerted the most prominent influence on surface roughness, with the depth of cut ranking next, and the feed rate being the least impactful.

This result agrees slightly with the conclusions of Zeqiri *et al.*, (2018) who documented that increment in the cutting speed values resulted in the decrement in the roughness parameters of R_a , R_t and R_z . However, the authors noted that increasing cutting depth also results in increasing values of the roughness parameters. In their conclusions, there was no mention of the impact of feed rate on the roughness parameters.

Figure 7. Surface Plots of the Response Variable
 Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

The surface plot of the response is given in Figure 7. Furthermore, the interaction plot of the cutting parameters is presented in Figure 3.6. In Figure 8, it is shown that interaction occurs

between cutting speed and feed rate when the value of the feed rate is set at 0.180 mm/rev. At 55 rpm, the surface roughness values gradually increase until it reaches a value of 155 rpm

whereby further increase in the values of cutting speed will only result in a sharp decrease in the values of surface roughness. The effect of other values of the feed rate in this interaction is largely insignificant and thus negligible. From the plot, a similar interaction is observed between cutting speed and depth of cut. Given a depth of cut of 0.35 mm, it is noticed that the cutting speed increases rapidly with increasing surface roughness. However, there is a sharp decline

when the cutting speed gets to 155 rpm whereby further increment in the values of cutting speed will lead to a rapid reduction in the values of surface roughness. A non-parallel interaction is briefly observed between the feed rate and the depth of cut. At lower values of feed, there is a gradual decrease in the values of surface roughness when the depth of cut is 0.35 mm. However, this value remains constant even with increasing feed rate.

Figure 8. Interaction plots for Surface Roughness
 Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Optimization of Cutting Parameters for Minimum Surface Roughness

The criteria factors were established to ensure that the independent variables (cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut) fell within a range that was economically favourable. The main criteria for constraint optimization was minimum surface roughness. The desired goals for each cutting parameter and response is shown in Table 3.7. In order to optimize the

parameters of the turning operation, numerical optimization techniques were employed to identify a point that minimizes the desirability function. Each of the three cutting parameters and its corresponding response (surface roughness) were given equal weight with a value of "3" to achieve optimal results.

The optimization of the experimental values based on the cutting parameters was executed using numerical technique in response surface

methodology (RSM) with the goals as presented in Table 3.7. The graphical representation of optimal solution of the optimization process is shown in Figure 11. with optimal values of cutting parameters of cutting speed, feed rate

and depth of cut at 254.056 (rpm), 0.183419 (mm/rev) and 0.254583 (mm) respectively. Optimal minimum surface roughness was found to be 0.663487 (microns) and a desirability of 1.00 was obtained.

Table 11. Criteria and Output for Numerical Optimization of Cutting Parameters and its effect on Surface Roughness

Surface Parameters	Roughness	Unit	Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Optimization Goal	Relative Importance
Cutting Speed		rpm	55.00	255.00	Range	3
Feed Rate		mm/rev	0.15	0.21	Range	3
Depth of Cut		millimetres	0.25	0.45	Range	3
Surface Roughness		microns	0.78	3.64	Minimise	3

Desirability = 1.000
Solution 1 out of 100

Figure 9. Optimal Values of Cutting Parameters with Minimum Surface Roughness

Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Based on the data presented in Figure 9, it is evident that the most effective values for cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut are 254 rpm, 0.183 mm/rev, and 0.25 mm respectively. The minimum surface roughness achieved with these specific cutting parameter values is 0.66 microns, thus, indicating an optimal outcome.

Results on Factorial Design

The results on the analysis of variance of the selected design model (2FI) is presented in Table 12. The build information on this design is presented in Sam, (2024).

Table 12. ANOVA for the Selected Factorial Model (Response = Surface Roughness)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	4.31	60	0.0718	9300.94	< 0.0001	significant
A-Cutting Speed	0.3994	4	0.0998	12942.41	< 0.0001	

B-Feed Rate	2.40	4	0.5999	77765.58	< 0.0001	
C-Depth of Cut	1.42	4	0.3559	46133.18	< 0.0001	
AB	0.0723	16	0.0045	585.45	< 0.0001	
AC	0.0016	16	0.0001	13.10	< 0.0001	
BC	0.0086	16	0.0005	69.68	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.0005	64	7.714E-06			
Cor. Total	4.31	124				

Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

The significance of the model is indicated by the "Model F-value" of 9300.94, suggesting its substantial impact. The probability of such a large F-value occurring solely due to random variation is exceedingly low, at only 0.01%.

Discussion of Results from Factorial Design

In Table 3.8, it is evident that the F-values for feed rate, depth of cut, and cutting speed are 77765.58, 46133.18, and 12942.41, respectively. This data highlights that the primary factor influencing surface roughness is the feed rate. The F-values represent the ratio of variance among sample means to variance within sample means. As the F-value increases, the model quality improves; likewise, a higher F-value for individual model factors corresponds to a greater impact on the overall model. Following the F-values analysis, the depth of cut emerges as the next significant factor influencing surface roughness, with cutting speed being identified as the final influential variable. The result recorded here is partly in agreement with the works of Singh *et al.*, (2013), Das *et al.*, (2013), Rao *et al.*, (2013), Kumar, *et al.*, (2013), Prasad *et al.*, (2013); Sam, (2024) who documented that feed rate had the most significant effect on surface roughness values.

The final regression equation, expressed in terms of real variables and utilizing a complete factorial design, is presented here:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SR = & -3.204 + 2.80 \times 10^{-3}X_1 + 0.23 \times 10^2X_2 \\
 & + 0.532 \times 10X_3 \\
 & - 1.56 \times 10^{-5} X_1 \times X_2 \\
 & - 1.52 \times 10^{-5}X_1 \times X_3 \\
 & - 1.23 \times 10^{-4}X_2 \times X_3 \\
 & - 4.35 \times 10^{-4}X_1 \times X_2 \times X_3
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

The interaction plot for the surface roughness values (Figure 10) indicates the behavioral pattern of the cutting parameters as it interacts with each other in the cutting process. The interaction between cutting speed and feed rate shows a slow steady increment as values of machining parameters are being increased from 0.15rev/min to 0.21rev/min. This interaction is proportional to the slow steady increment in the values of surface roughness. An almost similar effect is noticed in the interaction between cutting speed and depth of cut as the values of both parameters increases. However, a near uniform cut is observed between feed rate and the depth of cut as they interact with one another in the cutting process. Initially, at lower values, there appears to be a lagging in the cutting parameters with corresponding lower surface roughness values, but a rapid rise is noticed as the values of the interacting machining parameters increases. The main effects graph (or plot) of the cutting parameters for the surface roughness is shown in Figure 3.9 and it is a corroboration of the already established fact that feed rate has the most outstanding impact on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel. This means that increment in the values of feed rate will also result in a corresponding increment in the values of surface roughness. The opposite or the reverse of this also holds true. Following this, the depth of the cut and cutting speed are considered, as demonstrated in the main effect plot or graph.

Figure 10. Interaction Plot for Surface Roughness
Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Figure 11. Main Effects Plot for Surface Roughness
Source: Extracted from MINITAB software, 2021

Performance of the Three Models based on Predictive Capability.

Utilizing the model formulated through Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), the corresponding values for cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut (for each data point) was inserted into the ANN model to ascertain its predictive capability in comparison with the values obtained from the experiments.

Figure 12. Comparison between Experimental Data and the ANN Model

With a goodness of fit (R^2) value of 0.9979, mean square error (MSE) of 0.00301706 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.0549, we deduce that the model from ANN performed quite excellently when compared to the values of the experimental data as indicated in the graphical plot in Figure 12. This implies that the ANN model could capture the nonlinearities in the data since it could easily predict values that were close to the experimental data.

The RSM model also gave values of surface roughness that were close to those obtained from the experiments but its overall results and performance were at variance with those obtained using the ANN model and the factorial design. Apart from the inherent peculiarities of this model, the reason for this variance may be attributed to the number of data points (20) that were extracted from the generated data. Figure 13 shows the graphical plot of the RSM

prediction when compared with those of the experimental data.

Figure 13. Comparison of Experimental Results with the RSM Model

Despite indicating a goodness of fit (R^2) value of 0.9600, mean square error (MSE) of 0.1008 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.3, the results obtained using the RSM model had little backing in literature as only Zeqiri *et al.*, (2018) achieved the same results from their study.

Meanwhile, results obtained from the factorial model exhibited the same characteristics and pattern as that of the ANN. The factorial design model could estimate the surface roughness values with a degree of accuracy approximating that of the experimental data, although its predictions did not match the precision achieved by the ANN model. With a R^2 value of 0.9298, mean square error (MSE) of 0.0980 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.3, the model proved to be in concordance with some of results found in literature. The graphical plot of indicating the prediction of the factorial model and those of the experimental data are given in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Comparison of Experimental Results with Factorial Design Model

Consequently, it can be concluded that out of the three analytical tools chosen for this study, the model that demonstrated the highest accuracy in predicting surface roughness values, closely aligning with the experimental data, was

identified as the ANN model. This conclusion is largely based on the superior predictive capability, value of R^2 and MSE of the ANN model.

Furthermore, a qualitative comparison of the results achieved through the three analytical techniques is presented in Table 13. This comparison is based on the literature review conducted on previous works on this research area. The impact of machining parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel is classified according to their level of importance. The parameter or variable of greatest importance is designated with a value of "1," whereas the parameter or variable of least importance is assigned a value of "3." The parameter or variable with an intermediate level of importance is given a value of "2."

Table 13. Qualitative Comparison of Results Obtained from the Three Analytical Methods Based on Previous Works in Literature

Analytical Methods	1	2	3	Supporting Works
Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Feed rate	Cutting Speed	Depth of cut	Abdullah <i>et al.</i> , (2008), Rao <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Das <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Kumar <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Prasad (2013), Singh <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Rafai and Islam (2009), Senthil <i>et al.</i> , (2013)
Central Composite Design of RSM	Cutting speed	Depth of cut	Feed rate	Zeqiri <i>et al.</i> , (2018) only attested to the fact that increasing depth of cut resulted in a corresponding increase of roughness parameters.
Factorial Interactions of Factorial Design	Feed rate	Depth of cut	Cutting Speed	Abdullah <i>et al.</i> , (2008), Rao <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Das <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Kumar <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Prasad (2013), Singh <i>et al.</i> , (2013), Rafai and Islam (2009), Senthil <i>et al.</i> , (2013)

Source: Publications reviewed, 2021

Conclusion

The primary findings derived from this study clearly demonstrate that the feed rate exerts the most substantial influence on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel during turning operation. This conclusion is based on findings obtained through ANN and the factorial design methods of analyses.

Specifically, with ANN, it was determined that the feed rate exerted the most pronounced impact on the surface roughness of medium

carbon steel. This indicated that the values of surface roughness escalated significantly with an increase in the feed rate. Subsequently, the cutting speed and depth of cut were next in significance. It was observed that increases in surface roughness correlated with increases in cutting speed and depth of cut, albeit at a slower rate. Their effect, categorised in percentage, using sensitivity analysis tool of the ANN was found to be; feed rate 59.13 %, cutting speed 30.84 % and depth of cut, 10.15 %. This pattern of findings corroborated excellently with most

results of previous works on this subject area. Furthermore, data derived from the statistical indicators evaluating the performance of the ANN model in predictive capabilities demonstrated that among the three models, the ANN model excelled, achieving a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9979 and a mean square error (MSE) of 0.00301706. However, the limitation of this model stemmed from its inability to ascertain the combined effect or interaction of the cutting parameters on the values of surface roughness. In addition, the ANN model could not determine the optimum values of the cutting parameters that would result in minimum surface roughness when required.

The model developed through response surface methodology (RSM) demonstrated strong predictive performance, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9600 and a mean square error (MSE) of 0.1008, indicating a robust fit.

Using RSM, it was determined that cutting speed exerted the greatest influence on surface roughness values, with depth of cut following closely. Both cutting speed and depth of cut showed a direct correlation with surface roughness, whereas feed rate exhibited an inverse relationship

Based on its predictive ability, the model developed using the factorial method was also found to have a good fit with a coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.9298 and a means square error of 0.098.

Therefore, it can be deduced that when machining medium carbon steels on the Lathe, significant emphasis should be placed on the feed rate as the paramount parameter crucial for achieving the intended surface roughness.

References

- Alabi A.G.F., Ajiboye T.K. & Olusegun H.D. (2010). Investigating the Cutting Forces in Heat Treated Medium Carbon Steel when Turning on a Lathe Machine. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 8(1), 80-93. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17260531011034664>
- Das B., Rai R. N. & Saha S. C. (2013). Analysis of Surface Roughness on Machining of Al-5cu Alloy in CNC Lathe Machine. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, 2(9), 296-299. <https://doi.org/10.15623/IJRET.2013.0209044>
- Prasad, D.K. (2013). Influence of cutting parameters on turning process using Anova analysis. *Research Journal of Engineering Sciences*.
- Kumar K. S., Kumaar J.S.S. & Srinivasan A. (2013). Reducing Surface Roughness by Optimising the Turning Parameters. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 24(2), 78-87.
- Pankaj K. S., Novel K. S. & Ankit D. (2017). Optimization of Cutting Parameters by Turning Operation in Lathe Machine. *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering*, 5(11), 46-51. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4271/2014-01-9097>
- Rao C. J., Rao D. N. & Sriharic P. (2013). Influence of Cutting Parameters on Cutting Force and Surface Finish in Turning Operation. *Procedia Engineering*, 64, 1405 - 1415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.09.222>
- Das, S. R., Nayak, R. P. & D. Dhupal (2012). Optimization of Cutting Parameters on Tool Wear and Work piece Surface Temperature in Turning of AISI D2 Steel. *International Journal of Lean Thinking*, 3(2), 140-156.
- Sam, A.B. (2024) *Effect of Machining Parameters on the Surface Roughness of Medium Carbon Steel using lathe Machine*. M.Eng. Degree Dissertation in the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Uyo-Nigeria.
- Senthil K. T., Mahadevan G. & Vikraman T.R. (2014). Evaluation of Surface Finish on Machining of Mild Steel Using High Speed Steel Tool in Lathe with Normal Coolant (or) Nano Material Added Coolant. *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE)*, 11, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.9790/1684-11350109>
- Sheila T. N. T. (2009). *Effect of Cutting Speed and Depth of Cut on Surface Roughness of Mild Steel in Turning Operation*. Unpublished BSc. Thesis, Universiti Malaysia Pahang, Malaysia.

Sulaiman A., Moshood A. B., Temitayo S. O. & Isaac K. A. (2020). Effect of Some Thermodynamic Properties of Cutting Fluids on Machinability of Carbon Steel. *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5(2), 345 – 356. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46792/fuoyejet.v5i2.494>

Zeqiri F., Alkan M., Kaya B. & Toros S. (2018). Experimental Research and Mathematical

Modeling of Parameters Effecting on Cutting Force and Surface Roughness in CNC Turning Process. *IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 295(012011), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/295/1/012011>